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Pedagogik, psixometodologik va tabiiy fanlarga
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- 13.00.00 - Pedagogika fanlari
- 07.00.00 - Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 - Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 - Fizika-matematika fanlari
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- 03.00.00 - Biologiya fanlari
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and pedagogical sciences246
Tuychieva Saodat Melikuzievna

INNOVATION AS FORMS OF INTEGRATION OF EDUCATIONAL PRACTICE WITH PSYCHOLOGICAL AND PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

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Abstract: The methodological basis for the integration of pedagogical science and educational practice is discussed in this article. Innovations, their components, objects, signs, and opportunities for assessing the quality of pedagogical innovations are observed as a mechanism of integration.

Key words: educational space; innovations in education; innovative project; criteria for evaluating innovations; objects and signs of pedagogical creative results.

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada pedagogik fan va ta'lim amaliyotining integratsiyasi metodologik asoslari muhokama qilinadi. Integratsiya mexanizmi sifatida innovatsiyalar, ularning tarkibiy qismlari, ob'ektlari, belgilari va pedagogik innovatsiyalar sifati baholash imkoniyatlari ko'rib chiqiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: ta'lim makoni; ta'limdagi innovatsiyalar; innovatsion loyiha; innovatsiyalarni baholash mezonlari; pedagogik ijodiy natijalar ob'ektlari va belgilari.

Аннотация: В данной статье обсуждаются методологические основы интеграции педагогической науки и образовательной практики. Рассматриваются инновации, их компоненты, объекты, признаки и возможности оценки качества педагогических инноваций как механизма интеграции.

Ключевые слова: образовательное пространство; инновации в образовании; инновационный проект; критерии оценки инноваций; объекты и признаки педагогических творческих результатов.

INTRODUCTION

The problems of integration of science and education, as well as the harmony of theory and practice, have always been relevant. Undoubtedly, integration leads to the enrichment of the components of the creation of the whole based on harmony characterized by a new quality.

During the transition to the innovative paradigm of economic development, Uzbekistan has shown special interest in the integration of science and education. This is because the integration of these components of the socio-economic structure of society is an important link in the innovative development of the country. Education, research, and venture projects can solve the problem of ensuring the security of the mass development of innovations. These efforts aim to prevent Uzbekistan's economy from falling behind and to help implement the main features of an innovative economy and information civilization within the field of education.

It is worth noting that the integration of science and education, considering its practical directions, will have a guaranteed positive effect only with a clear understanding of the theoretical and methodological foundations and conditions for implementation. In this case, not only is understanding the necessary conditions critical for the expected success of integration, but also adequately assessing the relationship between science and education. Although this does not require specific evidence, many researchers and leading scientists regularly point out that the level of product introduction into the scientific education system is insufficient [1].

We objectively observe such contradictions in the following cases:

- The imperfection of the connection between psychological-pedagogical subjects and education, as well as the mechanisms of introducing the achievements of these subjects into educational practice.
- The need to introduce scientific products created through research into the components of the educational process and to turn scientific results into objects of educational practice, which highlights insufficient scientific and methodological tools [2].

However, despite these challenges, we can address these contradictions within the innovative activity of education, a necessary link in the socio-economic system [3]. By developing a mechanism to integrate educational practice with psychological-pedagogical sciences, it is possible to achieve successful innovative changes in the integration process within the socio-economic sphere, including education.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The analysis of scientific sources and conducted studies shows that there are several fundamental arguments allowing for a theoretical understanding of this problem in the fields of pedagogy and psychology.

Creating an innovative educational environment in higher education institutions can be achieved by integrating educational practices with psychological and pedagogical disciplines. However, until now, the acmeological approach, defined as "a system of principles, methods, and techniques enabling the resolution of innovation-related problems and tasks," was primarily studied theoretically and practically within the framework of innovation by A.A. Derkach and V.G. Zazykin in 2003.

Furthermore, N.V. Kuzmina (1993), A.A. Derkach (1997), A.G. Laptev (1998), G.P. Filippova (1998), S.L. Kandybovich (2000), O.G. Moskalenko (2000), V.N. Markov (2007), E.V. Selezneva (2007), I.N. Noss (2007), V.S. Agapov (2007), E.P. Kostenko (2008), and V.R. Orestova (2010) studied the mechanisms and methods of achieving innovation across various fields.

However, the possibilities of integrating educational practice with psychological-pedagogical sciences to create an innovative educational environment in higher education institutions have not yet been a subject of specialized research [6].

It should be noted that the concept of integrating educational practices with pedagogical disciplines to create an innovative educational environment in higher education has not yet been fully developed. The growing demand for psychologist-pedagogical specialists in modern society highlights a contradiction between the level of integration of psychological-pedagogical sciences and educational practices in creating such an environment [7].

METHODOLOGY

The methods include analysis of historical, retrospective, and theoretical-methodological sources; summarization and interpretation of obtained data; observation; interviews; questionnaires; content analysis; and qualitative and expert assessments.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

It is known that a methodologically well-developed integration process of educational practice with psychological-pedagogical disciplines is, in many ways, a special socio-cultural phenomenon. It represents a continuous education system that combines various types of leading activities and educational subjects, contributing to an individual's educational development [4].

Integration processes can be expressed within a three-dimensional learning space defined by the following coordinate axes:

1. Subjects of development, including preschool and junior school children, general secondary education students, higher education students, young professionals, and experienced specialists.
2. Systematic forms of continuous education, such as preschool education, primary education, general secondary education, higher education, and post-higher education.
3. Multifaceted leading activities that contribute to personality development, including games, cognitive, educational, professional, production, and creatively oriented activities [5].

Combining these three objectively reproducible and self-developing factors into one space allows us to consider the educational environment as a dynamic, developing entity [6].

The developing educational space is a constantly expanding and self-organizing system of interaction between psychological and pedagogical systematic forms and levels of continuous education, the activities, and the subjects involved in personal and professional development. This interaction creates an open, expandable, and self-developing learning environment [7].

Effectiveness of pedagogical research can be enhanced through:

- Providing conditions for the integration of education and science and introducing scientific developments and results into the educational and professional process to train specialists.

Supporting the priority development of fundamental research as a basis for creating new knowledge, mastering modern technologies, and establishing and developing scientific schools.

Raising the quality of training specialists and scientific-pedagogical personnel and improving the qualifications of professors and teachers.

Actively involving the scientific community in organizing and conducting research on current educational issues [8].

In general, the field of education defines not only research problems but also areas of innovation, which have become the primary mechanism for integrating science and educational practice.

Innovative activity in education refers to pedagogical efforts aimed at incorporating the outcomes of completed scientific research, development, and other scientific and technical achievements, as well as intellectual property, into the educational process. This includes the introduction of new or improved pedagogical products.

Practical pedagogical activity, therefore, involves the implementation of these innovations alongside appropriate additional research and development. This activity aligns education with the economic and legal structures of society, the laws of economic development, current labor market conditions, and the demand for educational products and services.

It follows that pedagogical innovation is the result of innovative pedagogical activity, which brings new educational effectiveness. This effectiveness encompasses social, economic, management, environmental, health care, and other aspects. However, it is not always feasible to directly implement the results of pedagogical research into educational practice. Innovations serve as a mechanism for transforming and applying these results.

A meaningful connection between science and innovation involves purposeful changes designed to improve, modernize, or reform existing educational practices through innovative projects.

Innovative projects typically occur in three stages:

Design Stage: Models and programs are developed as outcomes.

Technological Stage: The programs are implemented and put into practice.

Reflexive Stage: The innovative activity is evaluated.

Innovation in education focuses on changing and updating various aspects, including:

Socio-pedagogical changes;

Improvements in general education and professional training processes;

Formation of new educational content;

Development of new psychological-pedagogical technologies for education, upbringing, and the development of students;

Introduction of new communication and information technologies, and the design of educational and spatial environments.

The main directions of innovative educational activities include:

Ensuring maximum flexibility and non-linearity of organizational forms;

Integrating knowledge updates into all components of the educational system;

Developing human talent, creativity, and initiative as critical resources for socio-economic development;

Continuously updating educational technologies based on monitoring changes in the socio-economic and educational environment;

Ensuring the interaction of two innovative schemes: one for creating and promoting innovations, and the other for selecting and developing them.

As highlighted in the above definitions, the outcomes of psychological-pedagogical research form the basis of innovative pedagogical activity, providing the theoretical foundation for pedagogical innovations. This underscores the need for the integration of psychological-pedagogical sciences, educational practice, and pedagogical innovations.

Innovation in education is thus considered a factor that facilitates the integration of science and education. It supports the development of education by introducing scientific achievements into the educational process. To distinguish between the three interrelated types of pedagogical activity, their defining characteristics are often summarized in a table format.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the study of how educational innovations influence socio-economic development, the evaluation of pedagogical innovation quality, the development of necessary criteria, and the examination of educational institutions emphasize the urgency of this issue. Addressing the systematic problem of pedagogical innovations requires developing a robust system for evaluating their quality.

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